

Benchmarking HALEU TRISO Dimensions for Experiments from NCERC

Kristin N. Stolte^{1,*}, Peter J. Brain¹, Nicholas W. Thompson¹, Theresa E. Cutler¹

¹Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, New Mexico

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ABSTRACT

The Deimos and THETA critical experiment campaigns were the first HALEU TRISO experiments performed at NCERC and the first by Los Alamos National Laboratory in nearly 40 years. Deimos was the first with a focus on creating several benchmark configurations at room temperature, following a series of heated tests to determine reactivity coefficients. Following Deimos was THETA, which focused on creating benchmark configurations applicable to transport applications through the use of interstitial materials used in transport containers. Both of these campaigns are currently being evaluated for inclusion in the ICSBEP handbook. These evaluations have required the analysis of several unique uncertainties related to the fuel form, which have not been previously encountered in NCERC benchmark experiments. Discussed here is a methodology study for the dimensional uncertainties in the nested layers of the TRISO fuel.

Keywords: Benchmark, HALEU, TRISO, Deimos, THETA

1. INTRODUCTION

Critical experiments are typically documented as benchmark evaluations in the ICSBEP handbook. These evaluations are in part the validation basis for both nuclear data and multi-physics simulations. The rigorous peer-review process of groups such as the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Experiment Project (ICSBEP), enable benchmark evaluations to be trusted for high precision tasks such as developing cross section standards and new criticality safety analyses. As HALEU TRISO is a fuel being heavily evaluated for use in advanced reactors, there has been an increase in the need for information related to the fuel in order to approve new reactor designs, safety envelopes, and transportation limits. This led to the creation of DNCSH, a joint DOE and NRC program to develop new benchmarks relevant to HALEU manufacturing, handling, storage, and transportation, which has funded several experiment campaigns and benchmark evaluations to increase the validation basis for this fuel type. Two such benchmark evaluation campaigns are Deimos, which was designed using LDRD funding, and THETA, which was solely funded through DNCSH. The Deimos and THETA experiment campaigns were designed to represent HALEU TRISO filled reactors and transportation containers, respectively. [1, 2] Deimos also consisted of a series of heated experiments to determine the temperature based reactivity coefficients for this type of system. [3]

As Deimos and THETA were the first critical experiments using TRISO fuel performed by LANL in 40 years, the benchmark of the TRISO fuel presented a new challenge for evaluators. The HALEU TRISO fuel at NCERC consists of UCO fuel kernels with an enrichment of 19.9% encapsulated by four concentric layers of carbon and silicon and pressed together in a graphite matrix to form cylindrical compacts. These compacts were originally produced in the late 1980's by General Atomics for use in the CNPS experiments and have remained in the inventory since then. [4] These layers are delineated in Figure 1 and a compact is shown in Figure 2.

These layers, while great for creating an accident tolerant fuel, create a difficulty for the uncertainty analysis in a benchmark evaluation. The uncertainty analysis in a benchmark evaluation examines the

*kristins@lanl.gov

Figure 1. Labeled Tomographic Image of a Single TRISO Particle from NCERC Inventory.

Figure 2. Single Pressed TRISO Compact from NCERC Inventory.

uncertainties on the critical measurement as well as the mass, dimensions, and composition of each component individually. The goal of the uncertainty analysis is to evaluate effects of the uncertainty on the k_{eff} of the system independently. For dimensions, this requires holding the mass of the component constant as the dimensions are perturbed individually; however, for the nested layers of the TRISO particles, this provides an interesting challenge. This paper evaluates three different methodologies for completing the uncertainty analysis on the dimensions for the TRISO particles.

2. NESTED DIMENSIONS IN TRISO PARTICLE

As part of the benchmarking efforts for Deimos and THETA, a subset of compacts were destructively analyzed. This analysis included campaigns to quantify the thicknesses and associated uncertainties for the individual layers in the TRISO particle using XCT and high-resolution imaging as well as several different forms of chemical analysis to understand the levels of various impurities present in the fuel. [5] The measured thicknesses of each layer and the uncertainties are presented in Table I along with the measured packing fraction in the compacts.

Table I. Measured Parameters of CNPS TRISO Particles CNPS Compacts. [5]

CNPS TRISO Particle Parameter	Value	Uncertainty
UCO Kernel Diameter [μm]	493.06	± 17.53
Buffer Thickness [μm]	82.07	± 10.26
Inner Pyrolytic Carbon Thickness [μm]	30.70	± 2.88
SiC Thickness [μm]	33.67	± 2.06
Outer Pyrolytic Carbon Thickness [μm]	33.27	± 4.16
Packing Fraction [%]	62.2	Not Provided

It should be noted that the packing fraction in Table I is nearly double the standard packing fraction found in TRISO that is produced currently. This was measured using full 3-D reconstruction of XCT on the CNPS compacts. Additionally, it is higher than the mathematically possible close packing fraction for spheres in a hexagonal array. Thus, the first challenge encountered by evaluators for these benchmarks was how to obtain the correct packing fraction. This was achieved by creating a unit cell that was based around an FCC lattice structure, which when repeated throughout the compact shape created the correct packing fraction. A 3-D rendering of the unit cell, which has the base dimensions provided in Table II, is shown in Figure 3 with blue representing the UCO kernel, bright pink the buffer layer, light pink the pyrolytic carbon layers, and yellow as the SiC layer. Not shown in the rendering is the graphite matrix that surrounds the TRISO particles and creates the remainder of the compact. As the models for both Deimos and THETA are extremely detailed and have long computation times, the results presented in Section 4 are based on a single, infinitely reflected unit cell.

Table II. Base Dimensions and Densities for TRISO Unit Cell. For the unit graphite matrix, the base value reported is for the full width of the unit cell.

Particle Layer	Base Radius [cm]	Density [g/cm^3]
UCO Kernel	0.024653	10.3360
Buffer	0.032860	0.9600
IPyC	0.035930	1.9000
SiC	0.039297	3.2100
OPyC	0.042624	1.8700
Unit Graphite Matrix	0.127773	0.7000

Figure 3. 3D Representation of Repeating Unit Cell for CNPS Compact Modeling.

3. METHODOLOGIES FOR DIMENSIONAL UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

The goal for the uncertainty analysis presented in a benchmark evaluation is to show the effects of each uncertainty on the k_{eff} of the system individually. This is to avoid the complications that can be introduced by perturbing uncorrelated uncertainties as if they are correlated. To accomplish this for the dimensions in the TRISO particle, three separate methodologies were investigated.

3.1. Method 1

The first method investigated preserves the individual thicknesses of the layers that are not being evaluated by the current perturbation. This requires that the density for each of the layers external to the perturbed layer be adjusted to preserve the mass in the layer. Additionally, this requires that the size of the unit cell be altered to preserve the packing fraction in the compact. For example, consider the alteration of the SiC layer being adjusted in both directions by one standard uncertainty from Table I. The dimensions and densities for each layer in the perturbation are provided in Table III, also included is the unit cell width required to maintain the 62.2% packing fraction.

Table III. Summary of Dimensions after Perturbing the Thickness of the SiC Layer using Method 1.

Dimension	Up [cm]	Density [g/cm ³]	Down [cm]	Density [g/cm ³]
UCO Kernel Radius	0.024653	10.3360	0.024653	10.3360
Buffer Radius	0.032860	0.9600	0.032860	0.9600
IPyC Radius	0.035930	1.9000	0.035930	1.9000
SiC Radius	0.039503	3.0082	0.039091	3.4383
OPyC Radius	0.042830	1.8513	0.042418	1.8889
Unit Cell Width	0.128388	0.7000	0.127149	0.7000

3.2. Method 2

The second methodology examined holds the outer diameter of the particles and the unit cell width constant. To allow for perturbations on the thickness of an individual layer, all of the other layers are perturbed in the opposite direction according to the renormalized volume fraction of non-examined layers in the unperturbed particle. Again, the densities of each layer are adjusted to conserve the mass of each layer. Consider the perturbation on the thickness of the IPyC layer as specified in Table I. Using the base particle dimensions, the renormalized volume fractions for all the other particle layers are provided in Table IV. These fractions are applied to the value of the perturbation on the IPyC layer in the opposite direction as shown in Table V, which provides the final dimensions and densities for each layer.

Table IV. Renormalized Volume Fractions for Unperturbed Layers.

Layer Material	Volume Fraction
UCO Kernel	0.225189
Buffer	0.308073
SiC	0.214922
OPyC	0.251815

Table V. Summary of Dimensions after Perturbing the Thickness of the IPyC Layer using Method 2.

Dimension	Up [cm]	Density [g/cm ³]	Down [cm]	Density [g/cm ³]
UCO Kernel Radius	0.024588	10.4180	0.024718	10.2549
Buffer Radius	0.032706	0.9780	0.033014	0.9425
IPyC Radius	0.036064	1.7378	0.035796	2.0958
SiC Radius	0.039370	3.2523	0.039224	3.1694
OPyC Radius	0.042624	1.9083	0.042624	1.8333
Unit Cell Width	0.127773	0.7000	0.127773	0.7000

3.3. Method 3

The third method considered maintains the outer diameter of the TRISO particle and the thicknesses of the layers not being evaluated except for a single layer that is always perturbed in the opposite direction of the layer being evaluated. For this investigation, the layer chosen was the low density buffer layer that surrounds the UCO kernel, which means this method cannot be used to evaluate the uncertainty effects on this layer. As the purpose of this layer is to allow for the expansion and contraction of the kernel without breaching the integrity of the exterior containment layers, it was the most logical choice for perturbations. As with the other methodologies, the densities of the layers are adjusted to maintain a constant mass in each layer.

For an example, again consider a perturbation on the SiC layer. When the SiC layer thickness is increased according to the uncertainty in Table I, the buffer layer's thickness is correspondingly decreased. The thickness of the IPyC layer is maintained, and the density is adjusted to maintain the mass in the layer. The dimensions and densities for the perturbations are provided Table VI.

Table VI. Summary of Dimensions after Perturbing the Thickness of the SiC Layer using Method 3.

Dimension	Up [cm]	Density [g/cm ³]	Down [cm]	Density [g/cm ³]
UCO Kernel Radius	0.024653	10.3360	0.024653	10.3360
Buffer Radius	0.032654	0.9921	0.033066	0.9295
IPyC Radius	0.035724	1.9229	0.036136	1.8775
SiC Radius	0.039297	3.0413	0.039297	3.4008
OPyC Radius	0.042624	1.8700	0.042624	1.8700
Unit Cell Width	0.127773	0.7000	0.127773	0.7000

4. PRELIMINARY WORTH OF DIMENSIONAL UNCERTAINTIES

To test out each of the above methods and assess the effects of the uncertainty of each thickness on the k_{eff} of the system, an infinitely reflected unit cell, shown in Figure 3, was used. Each of the simulations used a total of twenty-five million active neutron histories, which resulted in a Monte Carlo uncertainty of 9 pcm for each simulation, and the parameters outlined in Tables III, V, and VI. The simulations also utilized Monte Carlo N-Particle[®] Version 6.3 (MCNP[®]6.3) and ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data libraries. [6, 7] The k_{eff} effects for each layer and method are provided in Table VII where u_{k_i} represents the standard uncertainty in k_{eff} due to parameter i . The u_k is calculated as

$$u_{k_i} = \frac{u_i}{2\delta_{x_i}} \left(k_{\text{eff}}(x_i + \delta_i) - k_{\text{eff}}(x_i - \delta_i) \right) \quad (1)$$

where u_i is the standard uncertainty in the parameter being examined, δ_{x_i} is the value of the single direction perturbation, and $k_{\text{eff}}(x_i \pm \delta_i)$ is the k_{eff} of the problem at the examined perturbation. For all the layers, except the kernel, the u_i is the uncertainty on the thickness listed in Table I, and the perturbation value was set equal to the uncertainty. For the kernel, the uncertainty listed is for the diameter, so the u_i is half that value. The perturbation size was set to diameter uncertainty, which is double the size of the u_i . The total uncertainty due to the dimensions on the TRISO particle is determined using standard error propagation

$$u_T = \sqrt{\sum_i u_{k_i}^2} \quad (2)$$

where u_T is the total uncertainty and σ_i is the individual uncertainties for each layer i .

 Table VII. Summary of k_{eff} Uncertainty Effects for Each Layer.

Dimension	Method 1 u_k	Method 2 u_k	Method 3 u_k
UCO Kernel Radius	-0.00225	-0.00018	-0.00021
Buffer Radius	-0.00245	0.00009	Not Applicable
IPyC Radius	-0.00071	-0.00002	0.00002
SiC Radius	-0.00051	0.00005	-0.00003
OPyC Radius	-0.00105	0.00015	-0.00013
u_T	0.00360	0.00026	0.00025

5. CONCLUSIONS

Understanding the effects that the uncertainty in the measured dimensions of the thicknesses and radii of the CNPS TRISO particles is key to the successful evaluation of the Deimos and THETA experiments for inclusion in the ICSBEP handbook. As the use of tight-fitting nested dimensions in a modern benchmark is unexplored, three different methods were presented in this paper along with results from a sample problem. From the results obtained using the sample problem, the first method produces results an order of magnitude larger than the other two methods, and several of the results from the second and third method would be considered negligible based on the Monte Carlo uncertainty of the individual simulations being large than the final value. If the values of the uncertainties from the first method are taken as bounding, these values can be divided by $\sqrt{18}$ to determine the final uncertainty in the parameters as shown in Table VIII. This methodology is the closest to what is typically completed

Table VIII. Final Bounding Uncertainties using Method 1.

Dimension	Final u_k
UCO Kernel Radius	-0.00053
Buffer Radius	-0.00058
IPyC Radius	-0.00017
SiC Radius	-0.00012
OPyC Radius	-0.00025
u_T	0.00085

in modern benchmarks that have layers of items stacked on top of one another; however, the evaluators feel that even when taken as a bounding value, this methodology overestimates the effects of these uncertainties. The evaluators also acknowledge that the effects are likely exaggerated due to the infinite reflection of the unit cell, and the contributions will likely decrease when applied to the full model of the system. Thus, the second method is most likely to be used in the evaluations as it allows for all of the layers to be evaluated, but more study will also be performed using the actual benchmark models before a final methodology is chosen.

NOMENCLATURE

CNPS Compact Nuclear Power Source

DNCSH DOE/NRC Collaboration for Criticality Safety Support for Commercial Scale HALEU for Fuel Cycles and Transportation

FCC Face Centered Cubic

HALEU High Assay Low Enriched Uranium

ICSBEP International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project

IPyC Inner Pyrolytic Carbon

LANL Los Alamos National Laboratory

LDRD Laboratory Directed Research and Development

NCERC National Criticality Experiments Research Center

OPyC Outer Pyrolytic Carbon

SiC Silicon Carbide

THETA TRISO-fueled HALEU Experiment for Transport Applications

TRISO TRi-structural ISO-tropic

XCT X-ray Computed Tomography

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